

EXPERIMENTAL CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES IN SUPPORT OF PROCESS MODELING

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the experimental and characterization efforts required to support the development of a finite element-based computational simulation of polymeric thermoset polyimide composite processing. The efforts involve calibration of material models and experimental validation of model predictions. To develop material models for thermosetting resin systems, neat resin specimens at various degrees of cure were fabricated and were characterized for chemical, thermal, and mechanical properties. Neat resin properties of interest include glass transition temperature (T_g), the degree of cure (DoC), thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, modulus, and viscosity. An angle bracket case study was used for experimental validation, which involved manufacture of composite angle brackets, and studied the effects of cure cycles, part thickness, and bend radius on the part distortion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing polymer matrix composites (PMCs), specifically thermoset polyimide composites, is a time- and labor-intensive process that involves imidization and curing of a thermoset matrix resin with reinforcements such as continuous carbon fibers. During cure, the matrix undergoes phase transformations associated with chemical crosslinking of the polymer chains, which leads to material property (e.g. glass transition temperature (T_g), thermal expansion, modulus) evolution as a function of the degree of cure (DoC) and instantaneous temperature. During composite curing, residual stresses are built up, causing geometrical deformations to the desired final part configuration. These residual stresses are due in large part to the property evolutions that occur throughout the cure cycle, along with mismatched coefficients of thermal expansion between the fiber and matrix, and the anisotropy of the laminate. The geometrical deformations often lead to the necessity of several iterations on tooling and process parameters to achieve the desired final part configuration. To reduce the number of trial and error cycle iterations, process modeling of composite manufacturing has been a growing area of interest.

A primary focus of process model development to date [1] is capturing phase change kinetics and associated material property evolutions to predict final part geometry as a result of generated residual stresses. A recent effort [2] investigated the effects of temperature excursions near the instantaneous, evolving glass transition temperature, and discovered that existing cure models lacked the ability to predict the residual stresses for processing cycles that included similar temperature excursions. Consequently, an elastic-viscoplastic model was formulated and implemented under the hypothesis that viscoplastic flow near the glass transition temperature resulted in a relaxation of the residual stresses

during cure. This model was successful in capturing the trends (e.g. increasing/decreasing) in composite angle bracket spring-in as a function of the processing parameters [2].

While the predictive capability of process models has improved, significant challenges remain in calibrating the underlying material property models as functions of DoC. First, the number of material properties that are necessary dictates a significant experimental characterization effort. In addition, the material properties of the polymer change rapidly and are not always uniquely measurable. For instance, the cure shrinkage and thermal expansion phenomena experienced by the polymer matrix often occur simultaneously. Thus, it is non-trivial to distinguish between these volumetric effects during cure.

This paper discusses the experimental and characterization efforts required to support the development of a finite element-based computational simulation of thermoset polyimide composite processing. We describe efforts involving calibration of material models and experimental validation of model predictions. To develop material models for thermosetting resin systems, standard experiments were modified and conducted on in-house fabricated neat resin specimens to isolate specific thermal and mechanical response characteristics. Material parameters of interest include T_g , DoC, thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, modulus, and viscosity. An angle bracket case study was used for model validation, which involved manufacture of composite angle brackets while studying a variety of process variables, as well as analysis of final bracket geometry.

2 MATERIAL MODEL CALIBRATION

The material modeling efforts aim to extend and validate the elastic-viscoplastic process model [3] previously developed for a toughened epoxy resin to a polyimide resin. Novel characterization techniques are used to understand material properties as a function of DoC. The results from characterization experiments are then used to calibrate the material property models as a function of DoC, which are subsequently implemented and used in a finite element framework.

The development of a process model necessitates calibration of a large number of material properties as a function of DoC and temperature and development of the corresponding material property models. These calibration efforts involve a series of material characterization experiments conducted on neat resin specimens with varying DoC. Then, a series of data reduction and optimization procedures are carried out to develop material models. Material models are being developed for kinetics, thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, modulus, and viscosity.

Material characterization for process simulation of thermoset materials is particularly challenging because mechanical and thermal properties depend not only on temperature but on DoC. To obtain property information at elevated temperature, one must account for the continuous evolution of the measured properties as the DoC advances. The underlying assumption for material property characterization and calibration in the present work is that reduced temperature $T_R = (T/T_g) - 1$, which represents both the instantaneous temperature and the DoC in a single parameter, can be used as a primary independent variable. This approach simplifies test requirements, data reduction procedures, and numerical material modeling. The reduced temperature (T_R) assumption has been demonstrated successfully for characterizing a toughened epoxy [3], but has not been tested for a polyimide. This work extends this approach to a polyimide resin to assess universality of the methodology.

2.1 Neat Resin Fabrication

To characterize material properties as a function of the DoC, it is necessary to fabricate neat resin specimens at intermediate degrees of cure, which poses challenges due to the innate brittleness of some thermoset resins at low degrees of cure, and especially thermosetting polyimide materials involving solvent evolution. Thermoset polyimide materials have two steps of processing: imidization and crosslinking. The imidization step involves reactions of monomers to form oligomers. This process involves solvent removal in the as-received materials and during imidization, which was not included in the model calibration. In the crosslinking stage, oligomers react to form a crosslinking network, which was the only step included in the model calibration.

Neat polyimide resin was purchased and contained 40 percent of ethanol in solution. Before fabricating neat resin samples, it was necessary to degas and imidize the material to remove solvent and form amide acid oligomers. The imidized resin (powder) was then manufactured into neat resin samples

with various degrees of cure using autoclave or compression molding methods. Figure 1 shows the as-received resin (in solution), imidized resin (powder), and neat resin film with DoC = 0.74 (solid sheet) at ambient temperature. Methods were developed to successfully fabricate high quality polyimide neat resin specimens with thicknesses appropriate for various characterization techniques (0.3 mm and 3 mm) and at degrees of cure ranging from 0.25 to 1.0. Neat resin specimens were subsequently used in material characterization experiments for material model calibration.

Compression molding methods were used to fabricate neat resin plaques for 3 mm thick samples. The thick plaques were ultrasonically C-scanned to examine the part quality, and the results were observed to be of relatively high uniformity. High quality compression molded plaques with DoC of 0.56 to 0.83 were achieved. Challenges were associated with fabricating thick plaques at lower degrees of cure. These neat resin plaques are used for thermogravimetric analysis (TMA) experiments to measure cure shrinkage (CS) and coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE).

The autoclave method was used to make 0.3 mm thick films with DoC ranging from 0.25 to 0.95 where the films were visually inspected for quality. Films with a lower DoC of 0.25 were extremely brittle and broke into small pieces, while films with DoC of 0.53 cracked into large pieces. Films with DoC of 0.74 and above, as shown in Figure 1 (right), had a homogeneous appearance and did not break upon demolding. These neat resin films were used for dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) stress relaxation mode experiments to measure modulus and viscosity of the materials at various temperatures.

Figure 1: As-received resin (in solution), imidized resin (powder), and neat resin film with degree of cure of 0.7 (solid sheet) at ambient temperature.

2.2 Kinetics Model Development

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments are commonly used to obtain T_g and heat of reactions using dynamic ramp temperature profiles. The DiBenedetto equation is often used to demonstrate the relationship between T_g and DoC for a kinetic model [3]. This relationship was also previously used for a toughened epoxy system and other epoxy materials [2, 4, 5]. However, polyimides present their own set of challenges when it comes to these experiments due to the presence of residual solvents and volatile production, overlapping kinetics for oligomerization and crosslinking, and decomposition at high cure temperatures. For example, the thermogram in Figure 2 (left) shows overlapping transitions both just below and just above the crosslinking exothermic peak. The rate of weight loss in Figure 2 (right) shows that degradation starts just above 400°C, and in that range crosslinking is still happening. These overlapping transitions make it difficult to define the baseline, which affects calculations for heat of reaction. This makes it challenging to use standard heat of reaction methods to develop kinetic models.

Figure 2: DSC showing overlapping events (left); TGA showing degradation at various heating rates ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) (right).

Due to the uncertainties associated with obtaining heat release rate from DSC dynamic data for polyimides, a different method was developed using a sawtooth temperature profile as shown in the red curve in Figure 3 (top). The sawtooth experiments with the series of ramps and holds were developed in a single modulated DSC scan to measure heat capacity (C_p) as shown in the maroon curve. The derivative of these heat capacity values with respect to time is shown in the red curve in Figure 3 (bottom). The peaks in the derivative curve are taken as T_g in the sawtooth profile with progressively higher hold temperatures. These T_g values were fitted to a logistic function to obtain the reaction rate model. Previous efforts had success using reduced temperature (T_R) to model the reaction rate of the toughened epoxy resin [4]. Similar approaches are applied for polyimides.

Through this fitting method, the rate model was expressed in terms of the first order rate constant k , shown in Equation 1. Applying the model to the sawtooth temperature profile (Figure 3, top, red curve) results in the predicted T_g values graphed in blue (Figure 3, top). The measured T_g discrete points match up well with the predicted T_g for the sawtooth profile.

$$\ln k - 10x = \frac{40}{(1 + \exp[-50(T_r + 0.05)])} - 53 + 28T_r \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: (top) Sawtooth modulated DSC temperature profile (red) with resulting heat capacity values (maroon); (bottom) derivative of heat capacity curve (blue) with peaks correlating to T_g values.

2.3 Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) & Cure Shrinkage (CS): Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

TMA using a TA Instruments Q400 was used to measure sample dimensional changes as a function of temperature and time. Neat resin samples of 3 mm thickness with 6 mm x 6 mm edge length were investigated using a preload force of 0.05 N. Samples were exposed to a sawtooth temperature profile which was characterized by a series of temperature ramps and isothermal holds designed to isolate the competing contributions of cure shrinkage (CS) and thermal expansion (CTE) at intermediate degrees of cure as shown in Figure 4, left. Isothermal holds provide information about the cure shrinkage behavior, while rapid temperature ramps isolate thermal expansion behavior. Unique temperature profiles were developed based on the initial DoC of each specimen. A variety of experiments were conducted using these unique thermal profiles and specimens with initial degrees of cure of 0.56, 0.68, and 0.82 to decouple the competing effects of thermal expansion and cure shrinkage. Figure 4, right, shows thermal expansion coefficient and cure shrinkage property models as a function of reduced temperature, which were developed by fitting the experimental data to the assumed model form for the properties (described below). These models will be combined with a micromechanics model and used to predict the behavior of angle bracket parts in the experimental validation.

Figure 4: Sawtooth thermal profile and thickness strain (left) and results of fitted thermal expansion/cure shrinkage coefficients as a function of reduced temperature (right).

2.4 Modulus & Viscosity: Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

DMA experiments performed on 0.3 mm thin films using oscillatory 10°C/min temperature ramps from 25 – 450°C, a frequency of 1 Hz, and a strain of 0.01 %, were conducted to determine the T_g using the onset of the storage modulus curve for the material of interest. The T_g values determined through these DMA experiments were often less ambiguous and more repeatable than T_g values obtained from DSC heat flow curves.

A TA Instruments RSA-III was used in tensile stress relaxation experiments to measure modulus and viscosity at temperatures below, at, and above the T_g (negative, zero, and positive T_R , respectively) to understand the relaxation behavior as a function of T_R over a range of environmental conditions [6]. Thin film specimens with dimension of 0.3 mm thickness, 5 mm wide by 32 mm long were tested at a variety of degrees of cure. Specimens were loaded into the instrument using a 15 mm loading gap and manually brought up to the desired test temperature. Care was taken to ensure the sample was under tension while heating. Once the test temperature was reached, the sample was pulled to a desired strain (0.1 – 5.0 percent) and held at nominally constant strain and temperature for 1 hour while the axial force of the sample was monitored. It should be noted that the low stress levels associated with these materials seemed to cause difficulty in maintaining constant strain during tests, producing a response that included continuous changes in both stress and strain. Stress relaxation experiments were conducted on samples with degrees of cure of 0.53, 0.74, 0.95, and 1.0 at a reduced temperature range of -0.5 to 0.2. Figure 5 (left) depicts an example of data obtained from a stress relaxation experiments for three reduced temperatures. As the reduced temperature increases, modulus decreases and larger amounts of relaxation occur at T_g ($T_R = 0$) as expected. At specific reduced temperatures, modulus and viscosity values were obtained, and the data was fitted and optimized to develop overall property models. Fitted modulus and viscosity curves as a function of reduced temperature are shown in Figure 5 (right).

Figure 5: Modulus as a function of time (left); Model fits for modulus and viscosity versus T_R (right).

2.5 Material Property Calibration

The properties considered in this work typically exhibit mild temperature dependence, with a steep gradient near the current glass transition temperature. In most cases, this behavior can be represented accurately by a function of the form [6]

$$p = \frac{a}{1 + e^{-b(T_R - c)}} + mT_R + d \quad (2)$$

in which p (or $\log p$) is the property of interest and (a, b, c, d, m) are constants. This assumed model form, which uses reduced temperature T_R as the independent variable, can be applied to α (thermal expansion coefficient), β (cure shrinkage coefficient), E (modulus), and η (viscosity). The methods used for identifying the thermal expansion and shrinkage properties (α, β) from the TMA experiments and the stiffness and flow properties (E, η) from the DMA experiments both rely on numerical optimization procedures but are different because of the nature of the properties and their behavior. The underlying models and the techniques used for property identification are described in previous work [6, 7, 8]. As a result of the data reduction and optimization procedures [7], material models are being developed for α , β , E , and η . These property models are then used to develop the finite element processing model for the angle bracket case study.

3 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF MODEL PREDICTIONS

This section describes experimental efforts conducted to validate analytical models of cure residual stress and part distortion in polyimide composite parts. The material model information described in the previous sections has been used to create predictions of spring-in angles and part distortions based on selected combinations of part thickness, bend radius, and cure cycle. Validation specimens have been fabricated and characterized in-house, and results of these experiments are reported in the following sections. Initial comparisons between model predictions and experimental results are presented.

3.1 FEA Process Model Development/Angle Bracket Case Study

The material property characterization efforts to understand thermal expansion, cure shrinkage, modulus, and viscosity are combined in the stress rate equation for our elastic-viscoplastic material model, shown in Figure 6. This model, along with our previously developed kinetics model, are used to create a micromechanics model, which uses a unit cell finite element model for each material point that models the behavior of both the fiber and the matrix explicitly. Then, a surface integration technique is used to obtain macroscopic stresses for individual finite elements, which include several of these material points within it. All of the individual finite elements together combine to form a finite element model of any particular shape desired. In this effort, the shape of interest is an angle bracket. Additional details regarding development of the FEA process model can be found in the literature [6, 7, 8].

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{\sigma} &= \mathbf{C} : \dot{\varepsilon}^E \\
&= \mathbf{C} : \left[\dot{\varepsilon} - \dot{\varepsilon}^{VP} - \dot{\varepsilon}^{TH} - \dot{\varepsilon}^{CS} \right] \\
&= \mathbf{C} : \left[\dot{\varepsilon} - \frac{1}{\eta} \sigma - \alpha \dot{T} - \beta \dot{x} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$\mathbf{C}[E(T,x)] = \text{Elasticity tensor}$
 $\eta(T,x) = \text{Viscosity}$
 $\alpha(T,x) = \text{Thermal expansion coefficient}$
 $\beta(T,x) = \text{Cure shrinkage coefficient}$

Figure 6: Stress rate equation for elastic-viscoplastic material model.

3.2 Composite Experimental Validation

To validate model predictions of the deformations caused by residual stresses, an angle bracket case study was performed. This study was designed to investigate how differences in thickness, bend radius, and cure cycle could affect part geometry. Table 1 shows the 8 different cases investigated to validate model predictions. The following sections describe fabrication and analysis of the angle brackets.

Case	Cure Cycle	Layup	Inner Radius	Comments
1	Cycle A	8 ply - [45/90/-45/0] _s	3.175 mm (1/8"), small	Two brackets were fabricated for each case
2			6.35 mm (1/4"), large	
3		16 ply - [45/90/-45/0] _{2s}	3.175 mm (1/8"), small	
4			6.35 mm (1/4"), large	
5	Cycle B	8 ply - [45/90/-45/0] _s	3.175 mm (1/8"), small	
6			6.35 mm (1/4"), large	
7		16 ply - [45/90/-45/0] _{2s}	3.175 mm (1/8"), small	
8			6.35 mm (1/4"), large	

Table 1: Design of experiments for model prediction validation for 90° polyimide/carbon fiber composite angle brackets.

Polyimide unidirectional prepreg was used to fabricate angle brackets for model validation. The prepreg contained about 15 percent by weight of solvent, a fiber areal weight of 146 g/m², and a resin content of 36 percent by weight. The prepreg was cut into dimensions of 177.8 mm wide x 228.6 mm long (7" x 9"). A double peak male aluminum tool with inner radii of 6.35 mm (1/4") and 3.175 mm (1/8") was used as shown in Figure 7 (left). The tool was sealed with mold sealer and then coated with mold release to facilitate part removal. After the first ply was laid on the tool, full vacuum was applied for 5 minutes to ensure adherence to the tool. Subsequent debulking was performed after every four plies until the lay-up was complete. A final debulk on the completed layup was conducted for at least 0.5 hours before bagging. The bagging sequence is shown in Figure 7 (right). At least three thermocouples were used during each autoclave run to monitor temperature at various locations on the tool.

Figure 7: (left) Double peak aluminum male tool with 6.35 mm radius (top) and 3.175 mm radius (bottom) and (right) bagging sequence for angle bracket.

Eight case studies with two different autoclave cure cycles for cross-linking (cycle A and cycle B) were investigated in this study. In general, the cure cycle for thermosetting polyimides includes both an imidization step and a cross-linking step. Both cure cycles A and B featured the same imidization cycle, which exposed the materials to approximately 300°C. The difference in the two cure cycles was in the cross-linking section, where cycle B contained a slower ramp rate, shorter hold, and faster cool down as compared to cycle A as shown in Figure 8 (left). The purpose is to demonstrate how different ramp rates, which affect CS and CTE properties, and cool down rates, which affect CTE properties, could affect part deformation.

Once cured, brackets are removed from the autoclave, demolded, and trimmed to final dimensions of 88.9 mm by 125.4 mm. Two brackets for each case study in Table 1 have been fabricated to date and analyzed. For quality control, ultrasonic C-scan, optical microscopy of cross-sectional area, thickness at various locations, and volume fraction information are obtained for each bracket. Optical images of the cross-section show no voids, and ultrasonic c-scans display uniformity as shown in Figure 8 (right). The average thickness for the 16-ply and 8-ply brackets was 2.24 mm and 1.14 mm, respectively. Bracket thicknesses were consistent, suggesting acceptable and repeatable ply compaction for the various conditions, which was also confirmed through the average fiber volume fraction of 60 percent for a 16-ply bracket. It can be concluded that all brackets manufactured were of high quality.

Figure 8: Cross-linking step variations in cure cycle A and B (left), C-scan images for each angle bracket leg (right) and optical microscopy image (bottom right) show high quality brackets with minimal voids/defects.

3.3 Geometrical Analysis of Validation Specimens

Of utmost interest is understanding and quantifying the geometrical deformations of the brackets that are caused by residual stresses resulting from cure. Spring-in angle is a common metric used to quantify how much the bracket legs spring inward from their original orientation. Spring-in angle is calculated by subtracting the cured part angle from the initial 90° tool angle. Composite brackets were analyzed using an X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) scan method and a FaroArm scan method to evaluate bracket geometry.

3.3.1 X-Ray Computed Tomography (CT) Scan

Experimental spring-in angles for the angle brackets were obtained through x-ray CT analysis using a North Star Imaging X50 225 kV CT system. The tungsten micro-focus x-ray tube was set at 65 kV and 140 μA in air. The brackets were mounted with tape on a platform. Using the system software, each bracket was rotated through 360° using a continuous scan. Radiographs were acquired and averaged; a total of 1400 radiographs were collected for each bracket. After scanning, the radiographs were reconstructed in 3D using North Star Imaging efX-view software. The data stack was then analyzed using Object Research Systems Dragonfly software. Angle measurements were recorded at slices approximately every 7 mm down the spine of the bracket. At each slice location down the spine, an angle measurement was recorded at 15, 50, and 90 mm from the angle apex as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Angle measurements were taken at slices approximately every 7 mm down the bracket spine (left) and at 15 mm, 50 mm, and 90 mm down the leg for each slice (right).

3.3.2 FaroArm Scan

An alternative angle bracket measurement method involved a FaroArm Edge coordinate measuring machine from Faro Technologies, Inc. PolyWorks analysis software from InnovMetric Software, Inc. is used to capture and analyze the resulting point cloud data. The software has the capability (1) to export and import point clouds to perform comparisons of experimental and model geometry within PolyWorks, (2) to generate polygonal models for comparing a tool shape with parts made from the tool, and (3) to perform angle measurements by using planes created from averaging the point cloud data. Two sets of angle brackets and the twin peak aluminum tool were scanned with the FaroArm Edge to quantify spring-in angles and understand the geometrical deviations between the fabricated brackets and the tool. FaroArm scans of the tool confirmed a flat tool surface and a tool angle of 90° .

Using the point cloud data from a single FaroArm scan, a plane was created for each leg of a bracket, and the angle between these two planes was determined as the measured part angle. An average spring-in angle for the entire bracket was then calculated by subtracting the measured part angle from the 90° tool angle.

Additionally, it was of interest to create maps depicting the geometrical deformations of the parts. Polygonal models were built from point clouds for both the tool and brackets. The alignment of the tool and the brackets was a critical step in creating the deformation maps. The bracket and the tool in polygonal model forms were aligned using a point pair feature, where up to 50 point pairs with matching locations on the tool and the bracket were chosen to bring the bracket and tool together on the same plane, with the bottom of the bracket apex touching the top of the tool apex. For more precise alignment, after the point pair method was performed, three reference target points were chosen evenly along the bracket width at the apex to bring the tool and bracket closer together. The bracket was restrained to allow no rotation about the z-axis and allow translation only in the y-axis during this exercise. The purpose of these techniques was to obtain the best symmetric alignment possible. After the alignment, the deviation between the bracket and the tool was computed for the entire bracket to generate a color map, which can be used to understand how processing conditions affect full-field geometrical distortion of the brackets.

3.4 Comparison of Experimental Results and Model Predictions

Preliminary results suggest reasonable agreement between predicted and measured spring-in angles. Experimentally fabricated angle brackets are being compared to two different models: (1) an in-house-developed AFRL model and (2) a commercial COMPRO [9] model. The AFRL-developed model uses an elastic-viscoplastic material model and the material property models developed and calibrated in-house and described above. The COMPRO model is a viscoelastic model that uses material properties built into the COMPRO program.

Experimental angle measurements obtained using the x-ray CT and FaroArm methods are summarized in Figure 10. The x-ray CT results in Figure 10 reflect an averaged value of all angle measurements collected for an individual bracket. The FaroArm results reflect the average spring-in angle obtained from the plane fits to the bracket legs. Results from the COMPRO model are also

included in Figure 10. These results reflect an average value of several angle measurements obtained near the apex, middle, and legs of the bracket. COMPRO results for cases 3 & 7 are still to be completed. The AFRL-developed model is not available yet, but will be included in future work.

Figure 10: Experimental and predicted spring-in angle results.

Note that larger spring-in angle values indicate higher spring-in or higher deviation from desired 90° part angle. Experimental results show that the 16-ply brackets had less spring-in than the 8-ply brackets, which is most likely due to the 16-ply brackets being thicker and, therefore, stiffer. Experimental results also suggest that the brackets exposed to cure cycle B resulted in slightly greater spring-in compared to the brackets exposed to cycle A. The increased spring-in may be caused by the faster cooling rate and/or the shorter hold time used in cure cycle B, but additional research is necessary to confirm this hypothesis. It was observed that the bracket angle radius (small = 3.175 mm versus large = 6.35 mm) had minimal effects on the geometrical deformation of the experimental brackets but seemed to affect the final part angle for the COMPRO predictions.

Overall, the spring-in angle trends from the FaroArm technique are consistent with the results obtained using X-ray CT scans, with regards to radius, thickness, and cure cycle. The COMPRO predictions successfully reflect spring-in angles of the same magnitude as the experimental results, but the trends from the COMPRO predictions are less consistent. The predictions reflect increased spring-in for the thinner, 8-ply brackets, similar to the experiments, but they also show a significant effect of part radius on spring-in angle, which is not reflected experimentally. Additionally, the COMPRO results do not indicate as strong of an effect of the cure cycle.

Figure 11 shows the deviation color maps from the bracket to the tool produced using the point cloud data from the experimental FaroArm scans for all eight cases in the angle bracket case study. The color maps reflect trends similar to the average angles from the X-ray CT and FaroArm results, but they also offer additional information not easily obtainable from averaged angle measurements. The color maps allow understanding of how the geometrical distortions change over the entire surface of the bracket. Generally, increased distortion is observed further away from the bracket apex, specifically at the bracket corners leading to twisting behavior. This phenomenon is observed for all of the brackets fabricated, but the behavior is more pronounced for the thinner, 8-ply brackets. The 16-ply brackets show less geometrical deviation compared to the 8-ply brackets. It is also observed that cycle B produces larger deviations from the tool compared to cycle A. Once again, a significant effect caused by changing the bracket angle radius is not observed experimentally.

Figure 12 presents an initial comparison of a deviation map from an experimental bracket and the COMPRO model. Both brackets represent an 8-ply large radius part cured using cure cycle A, i.e. Case Study 1. The deviation maps represent deviation between the tool and the deformed bracket after cure.

Figure 11: Color map showing deviations in millimeters from bracket to the tool.

Figure 12: Initial comparison of geometrical deformations between model predictions and experimental results (8-ply Cure Cycle A).

These initial results suggest qualitative similarities between the COMPRO predictions and experimental results. The predictions and the experimental bracket both show increased spring-in at bracket edges and corners. However, the COMPRO distortions are smaller than what was measured experimentally. As the in-house developed model continues to be refined with incorporation of final calibrated property models discussed in this paper, it is expected that the experimental and AFRL model results will become more qualitatively and quantitatively similar, with spring-in angle trends that consistently agree with experimental results.

Overall, it was observed that both experimental angle measurement methods show similar geometrical distortions and spring-in angles for each case studied. The color maps are one way to compare the deviation from part to the tool, but the overall objective is to compare the full-field experimental part distortions to full-field model predictions (as shown above in Figure 12), and the color maps produced from the FaroArm scans will be useful for comparison. The FaroArm scan method is quick and comprehensive, and the PolyWorks software is versatile; therefore, it is an effective method for making similar geometrical distortion comparisons.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Recent efforts to extend experimental and analytical techniques, previously demonstrated for toughened epoxy composites [2, 4, 7], to polyimide materials have been described. In particular, reduced temperature modeling of key cure-dependent material properties (modulus, viscosity, thermal expansion, and cure shrinkage), which offers a significant potential benefit for reducing the time and

cost of experimental material characterization, has been explored. The initial reduced temperature-based models for polyimide resin have been established and are being integrated into analytical predictions of residual stress and part distortion of polyimide-based composites.

A series of angle bracket experimental validation cases based on variations in cure cycle, geometric features, and ply layup has been completed. The spring-in angles of the brackets were captured using the x-ray CT analysis and Faro Arm coordinate measurement, and agreed very closely. The Faro Arm technique is an economical method for measuring part distortion, and its data can be used for comparing actual part full-field distortion to model predictions.

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